

Visual Localization in Complex Environments: Merging Traditional Geometry with Learning-Based Techniques

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Abstract—This paper presents a hybrid visual localization approach that combines classical geometry-based methods with state-of-the-art deep learning techniques to improve localization accuracy in complex and dynamic environments. By leveraging feature matching techniques, multi-view integration and integrating semantic segmentation, our method achieves robust feature matches, the effects of the different is evaluated. The evaluation is done on real-world vehicle data with LiDAR, GNSS/IMU ground truth motion and cameras, the system demonstrates enhanced precision in camera pose estimation. These capabilities are critical for maintaining accurate, real-time spatial understanding in applications like autonomous driving and augmented reality. The proposed method also supports efficient updating of scene representations, laying the groundwork for the dynamic maintenance of digital twins essential in XR environments and the influence of semantic segmentation and camera geometries is evaluated on a challenging real world data set.

Index Terms—Visual localization, Feature matching, Semantic segmentation, 3D reconstruction, Image matching

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, visual localization has emerged as a key technology for applications requiring precise spatial awareness, such as autonomous driving, augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR) environments. Accurate localization is crucial not only for determining an agent’s pose in real-world environments, but also for maintaining and updating digital twins – virtual replicas of physical spaces that support a range of immersive XR experiences. The ability to localize a camera or sensor in a 3D environment provides the foundation for creating, updating, and interacting with these digital twins in real-time, enabling more reliable and dynamic XR applications.

Traditional visual localization methods, such as structure-from-motion (SfM) [11] and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM), rely on geometric principles to triangulate 3D points from multiple 2D views. These approaches are well-established and robust to changes in scale and viewpoint, but often struggle in dynamic environments where moving objects or changing conditions can interfere with feature matching. Recent advancements in deep learning have introduced neural-based methods for visual localization offering increased adaptability to complex scenes. However, these methods frequently

trade precision for speed, and their generalization capabilities are often limited by specific hardware configurations, multi-camera geometries or scene types.

To address these challenges, we propose a hybrid visual localization approach that combines the strengths of classical geometry-based methods with deep learning techniques. By integrating feature-based matching, depth estimation, and semantic filtering into a flexible pipeline, our method can handle diverse environments, including dynamic scenes with moving objects, while maintaining high localization accuracy. The inclusion of semantic segmentation further enhances this robustness by filtering out dynamic elements such as vehicles or pedestrians, allowing the system to focus on stable and reliable features for accurate pose estimation.

This hybrid approach is particularly well-suited for applications where precise localization is critical, such as creating and updating digital twins for XR applications. Digital twins require continuous updates to reflect changes in the physical world, and our system’s ability to handle dynamic environments makes it an ideal solution for these evolving virtual models. Our method leverages key components such as learning based feature matching [1], depth estimation using mono depth maps [6] scaled with sparse LiDAR data, and geometric verification through perspective-n-point (PnP) solvers [7] with RANSAC [8]. These elements are combined with data from a vehicle equipped with cameras, LiDAR, and GNSS/IMU systems, providing a comprehensive and real-time localization solution.

The contribution of this paper can be summarised as follows. While there has been significant progress in both classical and learning-based localization methods, each approach has inherent limitations when applied in isolation. Our work builds upon recent advances in hybrid localization by integrating feature matching with semantic segmentation and depth estimation to handle dynamic environments effectively. By leveraging real-world data from a vehicle equipped with LiDAR, GNSS/IMU, and multiple cameras, we demonstrate how our approach enhances 3D mapping and camera pose estimation for the creation and maintenance of digital twins, enabling more robust XR applications.

In this paper, we first review related work on classical and deep learning-based localization techniques in Section II, highlighting the limitations and opportunities of each. We

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then motivate our design decisions in Section III. Finally, Section IV presents experimental results using real-world data to demonstrate the system’s effectiveness in dynamic environments and discuss future directions for improving depth accuracy and multi-view integration.

II. RELATED WORK

Visual localization has been a long-standing problem in computer vision, with applications spanning from robotics to augmented and extended reality. The methods for addressing this problem can broadly be categorized into feature-based approaches and more recent end-to-end learning-based techniques. Each approach offers distinct advantages and limitations, and hybrid methods that combine these paradigms have recently gained attention for their potential to harness the strengths of both.

A. Feature-Based Localization

Classical localization methods typically rely on feature matching and geometric transformations to determine camera pose. SfM and SLAM are two widely used techniques that reconstruct 3D environments by detecting, matching, and triangulating keypoints from 2D image sequences. These methods provide reliable results in static or mildly dynamic environments and are robust to some degree to variations in scale, illumination, and viewpoint. Popular feature descriptors such as SIFT [2] and ORB [3] have been used extensively for matching across views.

In feature-based localization, the process usually involves two key steps: first, detecting keypoints in the 2D image space, and second, solving for the camera pose using a PnP [7] solver in combination with a RANSAC [8] algorithm. Other geometric models like relative pose [16], [17] estimation with different types of scale constraints are also possible. However, using a PnP solver offers the advantage of leveraging geometric consistency through feature correspondences with a low number of needed correspondences and a strong (point to point) geometric model, ensuring higher precision and robustness, particularly when combined with RANSAC and minimal solutions to handle outliers effectively. These methods are effective at finding reliable correspondences between images and 3D maps, but they can struggle in highly dynamic environments where moving objects and scene changes introduce significant noise into the matching process. PnP methods also generalize well to multi-camera setups.

B. Learning-Based Image Matching and Localization

With the advent of deep learning, many new approaches for visual localization have emerged. These methods aim to learn scene representations and pose estimation tasks directly from data. Neural networks, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have been applied to learn robust feature descriptors, making methods such as SuperPoint [10] and SuperGlue [9] popular choices for feature matching. These learning-based methods can outperform traditional algorithms

in certain scenarios, particularly in environments where classical methods would fail due to occlusions, lighting variations, or repetitive textures.

Pose regression networks, such as PoseNet [15] and NeRF-based ones [18], directly estimate camera pose from input images, bypassing the need for explicit feature matching. While these methods enable fast inference and real-time performance, they often have lower accuracy compared to classical approaches. End-to-end learning based approaches are typically also less adaptable to utilizing different camera configurations or scene types without significant retraining. For example explicit geometry based algorithms can easily use different camera intrinsic parameters and also geometric calibrations of multi-camera systems without any re-training.

C. Semantic Filtering

A growing body of research has explored the role of semantic segmentation in enhancing visual localization [19], [20], particularly in dynamic environments. By identifying and masking out dynamic objects such as vehicles or pedestrians, semantic segmentation can improve the reliability of feature matching and reduce errors in pose estimation. This approach is especially relevant in scenarios where digital twins need to be constantly updated to reflect changes in the real world, such as in autonomous driving or urban XR environments. While some objects are clearly mobile, others may move infrequently or unpredictably. Additionally, static objects can undergo changes in appearance over time, such as seasonal variations. Accurately assessing which elements persist and which change helps maintain an up-to-date and reliable digital twin.

D. 3D Mapping

One of the main disadvantages for PnP localization is the need for 3D point data. A standard approach is to run a SfM pipeline to create sparse 3D points for feature matches like [11]. These SfM methods are hard to scale to large data sets and are not always necessary. In our case vehicle position data and sparse LiDAR point data is available, we replace a SfM like step for such scenarios with scaled mono depth based position 3D point clouds, per vehicle position. For 3D mapping, the integration of depth estimation methods such as mono depth [21] and LiDAR data has proven useful for generating more accurate and detailed models of the environment. While traditional methods like SfM rely heavily on stereo or multi-view geometry to create models of complete sequences and scenes, recent advancements in deep learning have enabled impressive relative depth estimation only from monocular images. This has allowed hybrid systems to improve the accuracy of 3D maps, even in environments where sparse metric depth data is available, as demonstrated on the KITTI [4] and NYUv2 [5] benchmarks and related works.

III. METHOD

We propose a hybrid visual localization pipeline that combines classical feature-based techniques with modern learning-

Fig. 1. Visualization of a local map of depth images for one position using all 4 camera images. The relative depth is obtained by [6] and scaled to sparse LiDAR data.

based components to enable robust camera pose estimation and 3D mapping, essential for creating and updating digital twins. The localization pipeline consists of four main stages:

a) Keypoint Detection and Description: For keypoint detection and description, we employ the DeDoDe [1] framework. DeDoDe allows keypoints to be detected and described separately for both query and map images, improving computational efficiency and flexibility. By decoupling detection and description, the system can pre-compute features for map images, significantly speeding up the localization process. After initial matching, geometric verification is performed using a PnP solver in conjunction with RANSAC to remove mismatched keypoints and improve localization accuracy.

b) Depth Estimation and map generation: To obtain accurate 3D scene information with minimal computational effort, we integrate monocular relative depth estimation with sparse LiDAR data and vehicle position data. Monocular depth [6] estimates are first computed for keyframes of the entire scene. LiDAR points are then projected into image space and used to scale these estimates to a metric space by fitting the relative depth estimates with a simple RANSAC shift and scale model.

c) Pose Estimation: Camera pose is estimated using the generalized PnP algorithm, which computes the camera’s position and orientation relative to the 3D map. This process involves minimizing the reprojection error between 3D points in the map and their corresponding 2D keypoints in the query image. RANSAC is employed to ensure robust pose estimation by rejecting outlier matches during this stage, least squares minimization of the reprojection error of inliers is further improving the accuracy of the localization.

d) Semantic Filtering: To handle dynamic environments, we integrate semantic segmentation to filter out moving objects such as cars, pedestrians, and other dynamic scene elements. The semantic segmentation model classifies regions in the image according to their likelihood of being static or dynamic. By masking dynamic objects, the system focuses only on static, reliable features for keypoint matching, improv-

Fig. 2. Semantic segmentation distinguishing between static, moving, possibly moving and appearance changing scene content.

ing the overall robustness of the localization in real-world scenarios. We train a custom segmentation model based on Mask2Former [12] with Swin-L backend, which has been pretrained on Cityscapes [14]. We have merged classes from the Cityscapes data set to obtain between static, moving (e.g., vehicles), possibly moving (e.g. trash containers) and possibly appearance changing (like trees or other vegetation) objects. The model has been trained with the Adam optimiser, with initial learning rate 10^{-4} and weight decay 0.05, resulting in a average accuracy of 97.63 on the Cityscapes validation set. This approach has been chosen to be independent of a specific set of objects, as we are only interested in dynamicity. While the current model is trained on a set of known objects, this approach leaves the option to enhance the training data with outputs of language-backed segmentation models (e.g. [22] and the many follow-up works), or by learning from observed changes over time, e.g. using moving object segmentation.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

a) Dataset Description: The primary dataset used for our first experiments was recorded from a sensor-equipped vehicle, and features an outdoor narrow street scene (reference removed for anonymisation). The car’s surround-view system is composed by 4 wide angle lens 1.3 Mpx. cameras, which allows to cover the complete scene. We simplify this map creation process by using data from the vehicle that is equipped with highly accurate GNSS/IMU and a sparse LiDAR scanner. For this data the vehicle orientation and location are known, it is sufficient to create local 3D data for each map image and compute the absolute position relative to this data. The global image location is computed by transforming the relative motion to the absolute position and location in relation to the map data. This approach allows us to skip a SfM like step completely and utilize the GNSS/IMU system for the mapping process. The sequence used for map data (ID 20240528_082517_40) consists of 6541 images along a 800m long trajectory. Each 10th image frame and position is used for the map data. Another shorter sequence consisting of

No. Views	Seg-mask	Mean err[m]	Max err[m]	No. valid poses	Recognition Rate*
1 Front		0.3	1.58	1062	0.70
1 Front	x	0.28	1.66	1046	0.69
1 Back		0.39	2.60	461	0.30
1 Back	x	0.31	1.60	395	0.26
2		0.26	1.56	1210	0.80
2	x	0.24	1.57	1219	0.82
4		0.27	1.29	1274	0.85
4	x	0.25	1.29	1285	0.84

TABLE I

Evaluation results: The optimal setup uses front and back cameras for complementary pose estimation, with a generalized camera model to manage multi-camera configurations. Side cameras add minimal value in this case, while segmentation masks help reduce false image matches by filtering out dynamic or irrelevant objects in ambiguous scenarios.

*Rate of poses where a pose is returned and the error is smaller than pose movement

Fig. 3. Two examples of successful filtering of potentially strong image matches of moving objects.

1500 images, (sequence ID 20240506_113214_02) is used for localization performance evaluation. The vehicle GNSS/IMU trajectory is used as ground truth for the quantitative analysis.

b) Quantitative Results: We evaluate the following performance metrics: Image matches, geometric verification (P3P) and pose accuracy using two sequences, one map and one recording that is to be localized. The evaluation is done for different camera configurations with and without semantic segmentation. Results are shown in Table I.

c) Qualitative Analysis: The best combination for this setup involves using the **front and back** cameras, which provide the most complementary information for pose estimation. A generalized camera model is employed to handle the multi-camera configuration, ensuring accurate pose calculations across different views. Side cameras, however, contribute limited additional information in this specific configuration. Additionally, **segmentation masks** prove valuable in reducing false image matches, particularly in geometrically ambiguous situations, by filtering out dynamic or irrelevant objects.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented a hybrid localization approach that leverages deep learning advancements within a classical geometric pipeline. This method capitalizes on the strengths of both learning-based and feature-based techniques, ensuring flexibility, scalability, and robustness across various environments. By combining keypoint detection and image matching

techniques and semantic segmentation with classical SfM methods, the system achieves accurate 3D localization while maintaining the adaptability to different camera configurations and scene types without the need for retraining.

Our experiments demonstrated the effectiveness of the pipeline, showing reliable localization in dynamic, real-world scenarios. The integration of sparse LiDAR data with mono depth estimations helped mitigate challenges in generating dense 3D point data. Additionally, we explored the potential of combining multi-view data and semantic segmentation to enhance performance by filtering dynamic elements, leading to improved keypoint correspondences and localization accuracy. The results highlight the promise of hybrid approaches in large-scale tasks, particularly in environments with complex and dynamic elements.

Future work will focus on further refining depth accuracy, add constraints to general 6DoF pose estimation. The addition of semantic segmentation shows great potential, and its impact will be thoroughly evaluated to further optimize feature-based localization in complex, real-world settings. Integrating semantic information into feature detection is another possible direction.

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